

SUBJECT INTEGRATION AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF A FUTURE MUSIC TEACHER

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Annotation: This article discusses the integrative approach in the process of training students of musical culture departments in pedagogical universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: integration approach, musical - theoretical disciplines, problem - subject content.

Introduction.

The need to modernize the entire system of teacher training at a university is associated with major changes that have occurred in the education system.

The main task was to prepare a specialist with a high level of professional culture and competence, adequate to the new requirements for the quality of school education. The effectiveness of solving this problem depends on solving a whole range of problems and tasks of higher pedagogical education related to the search for new approaches to building a teacher training system at a university and improving its content.

Subject integration in the educational process is one of the priority areas of the entire educational process, aimed at increasing the personal level of development of students as a result of the creation of a unified system consisting of combining the theory of problem-based learning and the methodology of the integrative approach.

That is why, in modern conditions, the process of training a music teacher at pedagogical universities should be aimed at developing ideas for the humanization of all subjects and their integration.

The process of developing the personality of a future music teacher is based on three stages of music education. The first stage is a music school, where training is not professional in nature, and each child, developing in accordance with musical inclinations, receives musical and artistic education, in which hearing, singing, movement, and playing musical instruments are used for an organic sensation of music.

The second stage is the lyceum, the period of professional musical education. At this stage, the teenager masters musical - theoretical knowledge

and performing skills on the chosen musical instrument. A necessary condition for the work is the study of musical theoretical disciplines such as music theory, harmony, analysis of musical works, and musical literature.

The third stage is a university, where all conditions must be created for a high professional level of the future music teacher. At this stage, the main principle becomes the principle of uniting all musical disciplines in the focus of the category of style - historical, national, individual composer. Revealing the main trends in Western European, Russian and Uzbek music, the teacher gradually leads young musicians to understand the mobility of changing pictures of the world and emphasizes the spiritual and educational possibilities of music over the centuries.

The solution to these problems formed the basis for the musical and theoretical disciplines developed by teachers of the TSPU named after. The bottom of the programs, emphasizing that the entire complex of musical and theoretical disciplines is subordinated to the stylistic principle. Thus, the Solfeggio course includes intonation of numbers from vocal and instrumental music from the European Renaissance to the 21st century. Solfedgio, dictation, and auditory analysis in the “Solfedgio” course make it possible to accumulate “intonation baggage” and form auditory experience in understanding the peculiarities of the musical language of a particular composer style or era.

The integration mechanism contains great potential for the professional development of future music teachers. Such basic concepts from music theory as sound, interval, chord, mode are further developed in the course “Harmony” - the science of combining sounds into consonances and the associated sequence of such consonances. The Harmonies course traces the evolution of pitch structures using music as an example from the 17th to the 21st centuries. This course expands students' knowledge of music theory to a new level - they become familiar with connecting chords in four-voice presentation according to the rules developed by artistic practice. The basis for connecting chords is voice guidance, which is formed from various types of joint movement of voices.

The course “Analysis of Musical Forms” involves familiarization with the basic forms using the example of musical works by composers of the 17th – 21st centuries. According to the established tradition, the goals of analyzing musical works come down to the following: to determine the form of a particular work, what feelings and emotions are expressed in this work, by what means of musical expressiveness a particular image is created. Sometimes the task is broader - to connect a given work with the style, genre, work of the composer, or

era. Going beyond the scope of the essay, it is necessary to comprehend it in the historical, social, communicative, and ideological aspects. Thus, the course “Analysis of Musical Forms” becomes the alpha and omega of professional musical and pedagogical training of future music teachers. We believe that the use of the principles and methods of musical analysis in the process of studying a musical work in conducting, piano, accompanist class and musical instrument lessons will help stimulate the intellectual and emotional-volitional spheres of our student’s personality, which leads to the formation of his value relations.

The content of all musical and theoretical undergraduate disciplines serves as an important factor in subject integration. Historical and theoretical knowledge, which is initial and unifying, can give the entire content of the educational process in pedagogical universities a special flavor. A look at theoretical subjects as an integrating factor allows us to highlight their didactic functions. These subjects give integrity and consistency to the entire educational process. They allow us to trace the formation and development of individual genres, forms and styles in music in historical development; they expand the educational horizons of students and their level of competence in theoretical and historical musicology.

An important factor in subject integration is problem-subject content, which becomes a link between the history of music and the analysis of musical forms, harmony and solfeggio. An example is the study of romanticism as an artistic movement in the course “History of Foreign Music,” which was formed at the end of the 18th and beginning of the 19th centuries. Studying the works of romantic composers F. Schubert, R. Schumann, F. Chopin, F. Liszt allows our students to expand their knowledge of the analysis of musical forms. Students will learn about the birth of the piano miniature. Chopin's Prelude in A major is a short piece written in miniature form of the re-construction period. A simple and complex three-part form takes on its unique appearance. Chopin's Nocturne in C minor is a unique example of a complex three-part form with a dynamic reprise, where texture becomes an important factor in dynamization.

In the works of the Romantics, a new interpretation of the classical sonata form and sonata cycle is given. A one-part “free form” is born, which combines the features of sonata allegro, sonata cycle and variation. F. Liszt’s great merit was in creating the genre of the one-part “symphonic poem,” which was further developed in the works of Gustav Mahler and Russian composers (Balakirev, Rimsky-Korsakov, Tchaikovsky).

In the style of Romantic music, new modal and harmonic means, which are studied in the “Harmony” course, play a vital role. In the works of romantic composers we find dissonant chords rich in alterations (“Parsifal” by R. Wagner – $D4\backslash 3$ with lowered 5 and 7 degrees, in F. Chopin’s concerto

e-moll – $DVII4\backslash 3$ with a lower 5th step, in F. Chopin’s Waltz op24 No. 2 – $SII6$ with a lowered 2nd step. All these chords are studied on the topic “Alteration” in the “Harmony” course.

Musical romanticism actively contributed to the development of chamber vocal lyrics. The melody of many vocal works becomes more detailed and individual. In the works of F. Schubert and R. Schumann, the path from a plot-based song to a “musical poem” can be traced. The genre of vocal ballad, monologue, and scene is born, which students learn in the Vocal class.

Specific facts and events studied in the History of Music course can act as a factor for integration with other subjects. Separately, we should highlight such concepts as genre, musical form, “style”, “sonata form”, “sonata-symphonic cycle”, which have a transdisciplinary nature. Integration of the history of music, harmony, solfeggio, analysis of musical forms with the help of concepts can be carried out at the level of interdisciplinary cognitive tasks and lessons of an integrative type.

The next stage in the development of the future music teacher’s personality is associated with master’s studies at pedagogical universities in the direction of “Music Education.” The traditional course in the history of music continues with the study of new subjects: “Main directions in modern foreign and Uzbek music”, “Musical culture of the countries of the East”.

Basic concepts in the subject “Main trends in modern foreign and Uzbek music”, such as avant-garde, aleatoric, neoclassicism, expressionism, dodecaphony, serve as the key to understanding the trends in musicology of the twentieth century, which are studied in the course “Fundamentals of Musicology”.

The study of theoretical and historical musicology, universal categories of musicology, reflecting the most general patterns of music (musical intonation, musical form, musical perception, theme and methods of thematic organization) in the subject “Fundamentals of Musicology”, contributes to the formation of skills to analyze works (subject “Problems of analysis of musical works ”), which gives masters theoretical knowledge, practical skills and skills for a holistic analysis of musical works of various styles, genres and forms based on modern criteria and techniques developed in modern musicology.

The programs we have developed for musical and theoretical disciplines for masters of pedagogical universities (direction “Music Education”) contribute to the implementation of the idea of bringing musical and theoretical disciplines as close as possible to practical activities based on the principle of integrity as a teaching method.

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